

THE ORGANIZATION AND SPATIAL (RE)PRODUCTION OF THE LANDSCAPE ON AVENIDA SOARES LOPES IN ILHÉUS – BAHIA

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ABSTRACT

This work aims to analyze the spatial organization in the landscape of Avenida Soares Lopes located in the center of the city of Ilhéus, on the South Coast of Bahia, and to understand how the past socio-spatial dynamics of the city reverberated in the current spatial organization. This is an exploratory and descriptive study with on-site visits that aim to carry out a survey of public facilities and the agents that work in the (re)production of the space on Avenida Soares Lopes. The analysis emphasized this coastal avenue as it concentrates tourist attractions and historic buildings that attract a constant flow of people from different regions of Brazil and the world, thus contributing to economic development as it generates employment and income on a local scale. A semiotic argument was also carried out, demonstrating the dyad of this Avenue: the same as a sign of Ilhéus and holder of its own signs, in which the main signs present on the avenue and the perception of the resident population of the avenue, the workers and the tourists that trigger topophilic and topophobic reactions in the perception of this space, as pointed out by Tuan. Due to the construction of Porto do Malhado in the 1970s, the avenue as well as the beach was formed due to maritime progradation, which caused the accumulation of sediments. The survey also highlighted a real estate appreciation process with the installation of high-income residential condominiums and commercial developments, such as fast-food chains, bars, restaurants, medical clinics and leisure centers. Therefore, Avenida Soares Lopes and its immediate surroundings require special attention from the municipal public authorities, since, in addition to being the main central artery of the city, it is connected to the Historic Center of Ilhéus, in addition to being, at this moment, an area that receives an urban operation with a great impact on the landscape, the Jorge Amado cable-stayed bridge that connects the Center to the south zone of Ilhéus. Therefore, the relationship that is established between society, the surrounding environment and the work for the formation of space can also be seen on Avenida Soares Lopes, where it has become a place of multiple signs and meanings and will be in the memory of tourists and city residents contributing to future mutations, both physical and social.

Keywords: Tourism. Cocoa Region. avenue.

INTRODUCTION

The geographic space and the social space are different (SANTOS, 2008a; LEFEBVRE, 2000), however the geographic space is inserted in the social space. The geographic space is concrete, not abstract, configuring itself as the product of the convergence between the material space and the social space. In this perspective, the material space is also the physical space, encompassing the natural space and the space that is the outcome of human work (QUEIROZ, 2014). For Milton Santos, geographic space is conceptualized as a fact and a social factor, which means that geographic space is not just a reflection, a means for which social action is carried out. The geographical space in this sense proves to be conditioned and a conditioner (SANTOS, 2008a; QUEIROZ, 2014).

Regarding the nature of geographic space, Milton Santos considers it to be a set of fixed and flux. (SANTOS, 2008b). In this way, geographic space as a complex of spatial configurations and social dynamics. Still in the context of the nature of space: “Given this context, we observe that, for Milton Santos, the nature of geographic space is the dialectic between inertia and dynamics, between the inert and the practical, between form and content, between material space and social space” (QUEIROZ, 2014 p. 155).

The production of space is compelled, while geographic space is understood as a product of relationships, and not in the sense of tidying up, but in constant self-creation (CARLOS, 1982). Space is the product of the production process that is established in society and whose main purpose is the reproduction of human existence, thus space being the result of collective work (CARLOS, 1982). The production of urban space and its form of organization involves the participation of society's components, and this takes place through the division of labor (CARLOS, 1982). In this sense, different historical moments will culminate in a socio-spatial production of its own, consistent with the time at which it is being produced, so the progress of the division of labor will result in different urban spaces (CARLOS, 1982).

For Corrêa (1995) urban space is configured as a set of land uses that are distinct from each other, but that are juxtaposed. Such uses will fragment the capitalist city into different activities, these urban land uses are in reality the spatial organization of the city. Although the urban space is simultaneously fragmented, it is at the same time an articulated space, each part maintains a connection with the others, even if the intensity of these connections is very variable in time and space (CORRÊA, 1995).

In the analysis of the geographic space, in this case specifically the space of tourism, it is based on the premise that tourism is conceived as a social phenomenon of human mobility,

in which tourism is the economic product (SOUZA; BAHL; KUSHANO, 2013) . Tourism as a socio-spatial phenomenon must be planned and managed through management that takes into account the idiosyncrasies of the globalized world. In the city, tourism has significant impacts on the urban morphology, given that the spatial organization of tourist cities, and especially those that carry out sun and sea tourism, specialize in the (re)production of the city to meet tourist demands (ROSCOCHE, 2013).

The structure of the tourist space contains socio-spatial segregation, through which the dominant elite induces the process of production and consumption of space according to their interests (ROSCOCHE, 2013; CORRÊA, 1995). In this scope, socio-spatial segregation can and is promoted by the figure of the State, which, when planning space, intentionally allocates public facilities for collective use, while interfering with residential segregation (CORRÊA, 1995; HALL, 2001).

In this sense, this study aims to analyze the spatial organization of Avenida Soares Lopes, located in the municipality of Ilhéus in southern Bahia, as well as to understand the production and reproduction of the tourist space on this avenue, which, in addition to having a historic center, also has its panorama of spatial organization aimed at sun and sea tourism. This research is justified by the need to know how the past organization reverberated in the current and future form of space reproduction, in addition to establishing the conflict between popular interest and private initiative on the avenue. This study also aims to support the planning of the tourist space insofar as it integrates the constituent elements of the avenue's landscape.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This is an exploratory-descriptive qualitative study, in which the main objective was to carry out an integrative analysis of the elements that make up Avenida Soares Lopes, and to understand how past paradigms reverberated in the current situation of the avenue. Exploratory-descriptive research is characterized by being a type of empirical research, whose purpose is to formulate questions, in addition to performing a holistic analysis of the object being studied (LAKATOS; MARCONI, 2021). To carry out this methodology, systematic procedures were employed for empirical observations and data analysis, simultaneously. The research also consisted of carrying out *on-site visits* , in which a systematic observation of the current spatial organization of the avenue was carried out, in addition to photographic records of the avenue and the historical and current constructions of the space studied.

In order to confront the analysis carried out through exploratory-descriptive research, a documentary research was carried out to rescue historical and social facts, as well as municipal and state plans and projects that resulted directly and indirectly in the production and reproduction of the avenue Soares Lopes.

Characteristics of the area chosen for study

Ilhéus is located under the geographic coordinates latitude 14°40'S and 14°38'S and longitude 39°04'W and 39°00'30"W. According to the last demographic census carried out in 2010 by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE), the municipality of Ilhéus has 184,236 inhabitants. However, according to the population projection carried out by the IBGE for the year 2020, based on the 2010 census, the population of Ilhéus is 157,639 inhabitants, with an area of 1,588.555 km².

Ilhéus is also located in the tourist area called Costa do Cacau by the Superintendence for the Promotion of Tourism of the State of Bahia (BAHIATURSA), this governmental body linked to the Secretary of Tourism of the State of Bahia (SETUR), regulated by State Law n° 13.204 , of December 11, 2014 (BAHIA, 2014). The tourist area of Costa do Cacau also includes the municipalities of Itabuna, Itacaré, Uruçuca, Una, Santa Luzia and Canavieiras, with access to Ilhéus possible via the BA-001, BA-262 and BR-415 highways.

Avenida Soares Lopes is 1.5 km long, adjacent to Avenida 2 de Julho and Rua Padre Luís Palmeira, where their confluence will reach the Jorge Amado Bridge, which connects the center to the south of the city. Beside Avenida Soares Lopes (figure 1) is the beach with the same name. Both the beach and the avenue were formed due to the process of maritime progradation due to the construction of the Port of Ilhéus, located in the Malhado neighborhood, in the north of the city.

In general, the transport and deposition of sediments on beaches is responsible for maintaining the natural cycle of deposition and, concomitantly, of the entire flow of sediments received at that location. In the case of Ilhéus, the region below the port (north zone) suffers from erosion, in which this region is threatened, whose coastline is under the protection of ridges (RODRIGUES et al., 2005). In the region facing the port (Avenida beach), there is growth of the coastline due to the addition of sediments that culminated in the formation of the beach and the avenue (RODRIGUES et al., 2005).

Figure 1. Delimitation of the center of Ilhéus and location of Avenida Soares Lopes.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ilhéus: from cocoa production to tourism production

The municipality of Ilhéus was founded in the 16th century, in the year 1535, but it was at the beginning of the 20th century that the city was highlighted as the largest cocoa producer in the world. Neves (2009) states that there were three important changes in the municipality as a result of cocoa monoculture, namely: i) demographic, ii) cultural and iii) spatial. Thus, the construction of Porto in 1920 subsidized the strengthening of international relations with European countries, and this relationship went beyond the economic factor, the European lifestyle and architecture reverberated in the behavior and architecture of the city at that time, being possible today. visualize this uneven accumulation of time in some city streets.

With the consolidation of cocoa cultivation, Ilhéus was the scene of great economic development, a fact that helped in the emergence of a geographic network, which connected Ilhéus to other cities in the region. For many decades, cocoa was the provider of much wealth and prestige, adding to the European influence, it resulted in a marked social inequality, this

phenomenon being described and denounced in some works by Jorge Amado, being able to cite as an example the work “São Jorge dos Ilhéus” which narrates the injustices contained in class divisions, worker exploitation and the Mandonist policy (COSTA; SOARES, 2016)

However, around 1989, the “witches' broom” (*Moniliophthora perniciosa*) caused cocoa production to decline, with a decrease in production and consequently the onset of an economic crisis that shook society's structures. Neves (2009), points out that with the onset of the cocoa economic crisis, the public authorities paid attention to stimulating new activities with the aim of recovering the economy.

Faced with this new reality, tourism was one of these alternatives to revitalize its economy, with the exploration of the city's landscape potential, with the decline of cocoa production, farms began to invest in rural tourism, aiming to attract tourists as a source of income. These farms, in turn, make use of the cocoa history preserved in the buildings and the landscape composition to attract the public that wants to know the local history and have contact with nature.

Moreira (2013), when making a historical rescue of the changes in the center of Ilhéus, states that the interventions and investments carried out in the center of Ilhéus, mainly with regard to tourism, demonstrate an attempt to intersperse the city of Ilhéus in the national tourist context. Due to economic stagnation, the idea of moving the city center appears as a proposal to boost the economy.

The old historic center of Ilhéus has become a tourist landmark in the city. The main stratagem in renovating the center consisted of the idea of using the history of the municipality itself as a target for contemplation of the city and being a reference in major events (MOREIRA, 2013). Tourism in Brazil, and specifically tourism in Ilhéus, spent decades being subcategorized in public administration. However, with the creation of the Ministry of Tourism by Law 10,683 of 2003, which, among other deliberations, instituted the national plan for the development of tourism and the encouragement of public and private sectors to promote tourist activities (BRASIL, 2003). In this way, tourism came to occupy one of the central positions with regard to government (MOREIRA, 2013).

With these strategies and actions, without a doubt, the city center gained a new look and these changes are materialized in the urban space, however it was not only the center that was subject to changes, but other parts of the city had to be remodeled to meet this new demand from the tourist economy.

Siviero (2006) states that the progress of tourist cities is linked to the notion of space, emphasizing that the physical elements in a visible way in the environment, mainly in the urban

space, such as attractions, equipment and infrastructure, contribute to this progress. In the context of the avenue it is no different, in recent decades there has been an expansion of these physical elements, serving as a catalyst for tourist activities as well as the creation of the cultural and social identity of this avenue.

In the work by Carvalho, Coelho and Bonfim (2011) whose objective is to propose revitalization actions for Avenida Soares Lopes, they state that in this sense planning is understood as a set of previously articulated and implemented actions whose main objective is to promote development in a of the urban space, in this bias the authors also complement:

In general, tourist planners, realizing the benefits provided by the activity, commonly restrict this social practice to a specific sector, resizing the cultural offer and implying serious social harm. Among the disparate effects resulting from tourist planning dissociated from urban and territorial planning, the privatization of urban areas, the deficiency in infrastructure to supply the basic needs of the living, the spatial segregation between tourists and visitors, in addition to the loss of symbolic meaning of cultural heritage by residents (CARVALHO; COELHO; BONFIM, 2011, p. 213).

A road that was and still is widely used for access between the Port of Ilhéus and the tourist attractions of the historic center is an avenue, which has already been titled Beira Mar, João Pessoa, Álvares Cabral and Mem de Sá and which today is one of the main postcards and bears the name of Soares Lopes (CARVALHO; COELHO; BONFIM, 2011). The city of Ilhéus, more specifically Avenida Soares Lopes, emerges as an urban tourist space, in which it expresses its materiality through some characteristics, namely: i) natural, ii) cultural and iii) historical, which come from various social contexts and symbolic representations of its residents.

Such statements can be seen when observing the landscape of the avenue, in which each place on the avenue has its own meaning and contributes to the cultural identity of this place. It can be said that the tourist urban space of Avenida Soares Lopes is a great source of meaning, both for residents of the city and the avenue, as well as for tourists (CARVALHO; COELHO; BONFIM, 2011). This relationship is characterized by a dynamic, given that the same physical element of this space can be attractive to the tourist and not have a meaning for the residents, and the same can occur vice versa (SIVIERO, 2006).

Burle Marx Project, proposals for “revitalization” and new spatial configurations

In 1986, the municipal government of Ilhéus hired the Brazilian landscaper Roberto Burle Marx to create a project for a public park for the area of Avenida Soares Lopes. This

project recommended and conceived in 1986, demonstrated a concern for the waterfront as well as urban renewal aimed at the scenic importance of the avenue as well as the promotion of tourism in the city (NUNES JÚNIOR; COSTA, 2019).

However, although with the completion in 1992, the project was not exulted in its entirety, given that several public and collective use equipment were not installed, thus, not fulfilling a social function of this public space. In this sense, the incomplete implementation of the The Burle Marx project misrepresents some of the social functions of this public space, as provided for in the City Statute (Law 10,257 of 2001), which advocates meeting the social function expressed in the master plan, meeting the needs of citizens (BRASIL, 2001).

Currently, what remains from the original execution of the Burle Marx project is the duplication of the lane for vehicles on Avenida Soares Lopes, sports courts and part of the implemented afforestation. With the continuation of maritime progradation, the area of the avenue was further expanded, having an aspect of empty land, which further contributes to the de-characterization and discontinuation of the Burle Marx project (NUNES JÚNIOR; COSTA, 2019).

According to the information explained in the Integrated Management Plan for the Seafont, some problems were found on the avenue, namely: i) poor infrastructure and deposition and accumulation of garbage, ii) underuse or non-use of spaces and iii) lack of public facilities (MMA; MPOG; PMI, 2007). Although this management plan explains the 2007 panorama, practically nothing has changed in the current spatial organization on Avenida Soares Lopes. The lack of public equipment that actually exerts its publicity corroborates with the underutilization of this space, in this sense the Ministry of Cities considers public equipment as facilities and infrastructure spaces destined to the most diverse public services, such as health, education, leisure, sports, assistance social security, public safety and others (BRASIL, 1979).

Currently, spaces on Avenida Soares Lopes that could be allocated public equipment and for collective use, were ceded by the municipal public management to private food enterprises, under the prerogative that such spaces would be idle. In addition, the implementation of these private undertakings was conditioned to the concession by the establishment of the placement of *playgrounds*, tables and chairs, however the use is only given by pedestrians who consume on the spot.

From the Burle Marx project until now, what has been discussed for Avenida Soares Lopes are revitalization proposals. However, it should be noted that in the conjecture of the Avenue it is not a revitalization, given that this term erases previous meanings (the previous

history itself) and imprinted other meanings, directions and meanings in that place. The concept and practice of revitalization minimizes the previous tradition, establishing a new meaning for that place (PINHO, 2017).

On Avenida Soares Lopes, public and private interest overlap. An example of this phenomenon was the attempt to install the Tribuna de Justiça da Bahia (TJ Bahia) which would occupy a total area of 9,793.70 m² on Avenida beach. Such construction would result in the deforestation of green areas, such as the removal of sandbank species, undergrowth and dense vegetation, as well as the destruction of coastal cords (PINHEIRO et al., 2023).

Semiotic analysis: Avenida Soares Lopes as a sign and holder of signs

A road that was and still is widely used for access between the Port of Ilhéus and the tourist attractions of the historic center is an avenue, which has already been titled Beira Mar, João Pessoa, Álvares Cabral and Mem de Sá and which today is one of the main postcards and bears the name of Soares Lopes.

The analysis of the avenue brings with it the dyad: itself as a sign of the municipality of Ilhéus and holder of its own signs that are part of its composition. In order to understand this duality with regard to the signs and meanings invoked in the study of this avenue, it is important to rescue the concepts of Semiotics and put them in evidence.

According to Deely (1990, p. 124) semiotics “Is the knowledge about semiosis, the theoretical explanation about the signs and what they do. It is the history of attempts to explain what sustains semiosis and makes it possible, namely, the sign”. Thus, it can be inferred that Semiotics aims to investigate the actions of the sign, and the function of signs is to communicate ideas through messages (BERTOL, 2002).

Thus, Semiotics is the study of the construction of meaning, dedicated to the study of the sign, that is, that which gives meaning to something. In turn, communication is a tool that enables interaction between human beings, so the non-verbal communication that takes place through images, codes, symbols is materialized in the landscape, in the city and in the neighborhood.

In this way, both Soares Lopes as a sign and the signs that compose it are perceived by social actors, and this perception is different for each one. According to Nogueira (1998) it is impossible to apprehend all the signs of a city, for example, since all individuals establish their own relationship with the place, in a trajectory that in essence is always unique.

Individuals from Ilheus or not who were spectators of Soares Lopes in the past have a prior and current perception of this avenue, the changes that occur over time awaken a sentimental memory, a feeling that can be topophilic or topophobic of this place and its signs, these being a feeling of belonging to the place or repulsion for it, respectively, as pointed out by Yi-Fu Tuan.

The people who travel, frequent, live and live in Soares Lopes have different perceptions, these social actors from different social classes, different worldviews are called flanneur, this term in French which is understood as “observer” describes these social actors who establish another level of relationship with this place, which is based on their experience.

The perception of this place, whether by the resident of the avenue, by the person who works or even by the tourist who visits, helps to shape history, and the reflection of this are the changes that have occurred in the last 50 years, visible structural changes in the landscape such as houses, commerce, as well as changes in society's values and paradigms, given that signs can be material as well as immaterial like non-verbal language.

Avenida Soares Lopes screams, and its expressive cry reverberates through the decades, and is heard by different generations, who are responsible for the constant changes in this landscape, which adapts to the times, bringing marks of contemporaneity and society's values.

In the itinerary one can analyze mansions, restaurants, chapels. There is the building of the Adonias Filho Library and the João Mangabeira archive - which was formerly known to be the Grupo Escolar General Osório, it is noticed when analyzing the architecture of the library, the style of imperial construction, having threshing floors and eaves, balusters and curved details carved into the walls, demonstrating the great European influence on the avenue's history. According to Freitas and Silva (2014) public libraries play a fundamental role in the dissemination of information and knowledge, thus making it accessible, making it possible for different social classes to use it. According to Freitas e Silva (2014, p.114) further reinforcing that:

The public library, as an information provider, must meet the informational needs of the user community it serves. Its function is to generate knowledge, through the provision of information, as information and knowledge go hand in hand, thus becoming a source of knowledge that fosters social inclusion and the practice of citizenship.

Cine Santa Clara has a structure that recalls the standards of construction of food franchises, in addition to the social contrast that this façade leaves in the landscape, it influences the collective imagination of the avenue; the squares Ruy Barbosa, Dom Pedro and Castro

Alves (popularly known as Praça da Irene) these squares have important functional values both from the tourist point of view and for the residents themselves, the squares serve as a meeting point, as places that provide appreciation of the landscape, in addition to having many pieces of equipment for practicing sports and collective toys for children (VIEIRO; BARBOSA-FILHO, 2009).

These squares, in addition to having a functional value, also have an aesthetic and symbolic value. Vieiro and Barbosa-Filho (2009) state: “The Aesthetic and Symbolic Values represent the function of squares as reference and scenic objects of the urban landscape, in addition to playing an important role in the identity of a municipality, neighborhood or street”. The squares are also related to the history and culture of that place, serving as dialogic spaces, being of common good to the whole society (VIEIRO; BARBOSA-FILHO, 2009).

In addition, the Luís Eduardo Magalhães Convention Center, Concha Acústica, some sports areas and beaches are also located on the avenue. The Convention Center is an example in the landscape of modernist architecture, which in turn is avant-garde whose characteristic is the use of unusual shapes and which always refers to futuristic models, ahead of their own time. In addition to being aesthetically leafy, these constructions preserve the social and functional function of the space.

Figure 2. Signs on Avenida Soares Lopes, Ilhéus – Bahia.

Figure A: Convention Center; Figure B: Adonias Filho Library; Figure C: Cine Santa Clara; Figure D: Cathedral of São Sebastião; Figure E: Castro Alves Square; Figure F: Beginning of Avenida Soares Lopes.

Source: authors, 2019.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

on-site research and systematic observation, it was found that Avenida Soares Lopes has its own identity, which is endowed with signs and meanings. Over the decades, the avenue has been produced and reproduced according to the demands of the resident population, as well as its spatial organization aimed at meeting tourist demand.

From previous projects to the present, it is clear that on Avenida Soares Lopes there is a conflict between public and private power and the interest of the Ilheense population. In view of the panorama explained in this work, it is necessary to implement plans and projects that allow to take advantage of the public, cultural and touristic space of the avenue in a sustainable way, and provided with basic infrastructure.

The use of Avenida Soares Lopes as a public space that actually carries out its advertising, permeates the containment of real estate speculation (as recommended in the City Statute), recognition, appreciation and maintenance of historical signs and public equipment by the municipal public management and the population. It is also emphasized the need to instrumentalize tourism as an economic activity and promoter of local and regional development.

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